

RADIANT-CREATOR WORKSHOP

Dynamic Value Chain in Action! Yellow pea and beyond

Date: 16 – 17 May 2024, Melfi, Italy

Hosted by: HiWeiss SRL

Contents

Contents	2
Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction	4
1.1 Background to HiWeiss and objectives	4
1.2 Workshop framework and participants.....	6
2. Presentations, Posters and & Round Table.....	6
2.1 Presentations Overview	6
Marta W. Vasconcelos, RADIANT coordinator	7
Michael Atzwanger, HiWeiss president	7
2.2 Poster Session & 'Stretching Puzzle'.....	11
2.3 Round Table Discussion with Policy & Food Industry Experts	11
3. Visit to HiWeiss Industrial site	13
4. Lunch prepared by Melfi Istituto Alberghiero with HiWeiss products.	14
5. Focus groups (Farmers and Consumers)	16
A. Farmers Focus Group (16th May)	16
B. Consumers Focus Group (17 th May).....	19
6. Annex I – Workshop Program.....	22

Executive Summary

This CREATOR workshop focused on biorefining of '**yellow pea**', and on practical actions which have and are being implemented to commercialise protein isolates of various forms. Here the value chain was presented as more akin to a puzzle (than a chain), providing several flexible options that can be utilised or avoided to in a dynamic fashion to ensure commercial efficacy; and to balance that efficacy with economic, environmental, and social objectives. In addition, focused group activities were carried out to discern the basis of farmer- and -consumer-choices regarding UC/UC-based product production and purchase (respectively).

1. Introduction

1.1 Background to HiWeiss and objectives

HiWeiss Srl (<https://hiweiss.com/>) is an innovative start-up that has carried out applied research in South Tyrol (Italy) since 2018 for the development, production, and marketing of new plant-based protein products, isolates, and concentrates, as well as derived products such as '*High Moisture Extrusion and Texturized Vegetable Protein*'. The HiWeiss products are produced within a controlled value chain using conservation agriculture (CA) farming techniques, and innovation also includes the enhancement of co-products and energy recovery, in accordance with the principles of 'circular bioeconomy'.

The reference market provides undifferentiated vegetable protein products, which are widely consumed, and provide nutritional characteristics but lack information on provenance. The HiWeiss company's mission is to industrialise an innovative process that, compared to its competitors, does not use hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid, or ethanol. The low environmental impact products may therefore lead to the advanced manufacturing of new high quality isolated and concentrated vegetable protein-based food ingredients, which are also characterised by specific advantageous functional properties for use across (at least) the food industry. Their vision is to create a market opportunity and value-added benefits along the entire production chain; through innovative processes and products of high quality, integrated into a reliable system of total- and food safe-traceability based on use of blockchain digital node certification technology – as a key characteristic of transparent circular bioeconomy.

The starting material (soybeans and peas, alfalfa, buckwheat, and maize) comes from a value chain that involves farmers, starting from the seed, selected and characterized from the genetic point of view for the specificity of the processing-ease/-effectiveness and final use. Also, sustainable cultivation through diversification and crop rotations offers low carbon footprint of raw materials, to yield an ethically produced and competitive ingredient in terms of sustainable

production and territorial character.

Between May 2020 and 2023, HiWeiss GmbH was the shareholder of a farm. The farm is now managed by three HiWeiss partners. The farm size is about 100 ha, divided into three portions: in the provinces of Vicenza and Venice in the Northeastern part of Italy. It has been managed following CA approaches since 2005 with continuous no-till, crop rotation and the use of multiple species cover crops. HiWeiss, in collaboration with this farm, implement the CA farming practices with tailored made sensors to improve production and sustainability of the process and traceable ecosystem service benefits that are delivered to the production system and communities regionally. Some services may be remunerated in the future through new markets (in addition to food), such as carbon sequestration.

In RADIANT project, HiWeiss is an AURORA Farm lead, with multiple UCs grown with CA and play an important role as:

1. dynamic (short) value chains (DVC), from Farm to Fork;
2. CA as agroecological farming practice for UCs crops. Testing crops yield, their nutritional and organoleptic value and processing aptitude for added value; and,
3. circular bioeconomy in action, including creation of new multifunctional products and co-products (protein isolates, plus crop protection agents/biostimulants).

The main objective of this workshop was to understand the DVC of the underutilised crop (UC) yellow pea, based on HiWeiss' experience. During the workshop, there were several lectures focussing on the yellow pea value chain, CA, UCs breeding, UCs processing, and biostimulants. In addition, a round table discussion was held with various experts from the different players of the value chain, as well as a tour of HiWeiss industrial-production site where participants visited the barley malt production plant, and the new future facility for HiWeiss plant protein production. A poster session and a 'stretching puzzle' session were organised with farmers and participants. In parallel, focus groups were held with

farmers and consumers led by JHI experts.

The workshop ended with a lunch organised by the 'Melfi Istituto Alberghiero' school's culinary students featuring a variety of dishes prepared using HiWeiss products (plant-based protein).

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

During the two days of the event over 45 participants attended the different activities carried at this CREATOR workshop. More specifically: 35 people attended the presentations and field visit, and around 14 farmers and 19 consumers participated in focus groups.

2. Presentations, Posters and & Round Table

A series of presentations and discussions given at the beginning of the event are summarized below. Presentations can also be found [here](#).

2.1 Presentations Overview

This workshop was organised in six sessions over the two days (16-17th May, '24).

Session 1. Welcome & Radiant project presentation

Michael Atzwanger, HiWeiss president, gave a short introduction to the workshop and the HiWeiss company followed by Marta W. Vasconcelos, RADIANT coordinator, who presented an overview of the RADIANT project.

Michael Atzwanger, HiWeiss
president

Marta W. Vasconcelos, RADIANT
coordinator

Session 2 - Underutilised Crop Breeding and Seed Production

Diego Rubiales, CSIC, Spain

Diego Rubiales is a Professor at CSIC (Spain), plant researcher and breeder with extensive experience in participation and coordination of international research on legumes and cereals. During his talk, Dr Rubiales spoke about improving peas and fava beans for Mediterranean environments using breeding techniques and the remarkable progress identifying variants with resistance to stresses using genetic resources.

Paolo Annichiarico, CREA Lodi, Italy

Paolo Annichiarico is the Director of the Research Centre for Animal Production and Aquaculture, Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA, Lodi, Italy). Paolo has an extensive experience in genetic improvement and genetic resources of feed grain legumes and forage crops and in breeding strategies based on ecophysiological, evolutionary and farmer-participatory approaches. In his talk, he spoke about new pea selections for Italian environments obtained through a genomic, agro-ecological approach and farmer participation approach.

Sophia Ghitarrini, PSB seed company, Italy

Sophia Ghitarrini is a breeder at SOCIETÀ PRODUTTORI SEMENTI S.p.A. company in Italy. Sophia provided an industrial perspective on how to obtain new legume varieties through breeding and the challenges the industry faces in certifying new varieties and producing certified seeds.

Session 3 - Carbon Farming & UCs Processing

Marco Acutis, Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy

Marco Acutis is a Professor of Agronomy and Methodology of Experimentation at the University of Milan. His research focuses on the modelling of cultivation systems, with particular emphasis on soil, environmental impact, and climate change. In this workshop, Professor Acutis explained the functioning of the Voluntary Carbon Market in Europe, discussed methods for monitoring soil carbon through various models, and outlined

strategies for carbon sequestration in agriculture as valued by the European Union (CA, precision agriculture, carbon farming...).

Francesco Morari, Università degli Studi di Padova, Italy

Francesco Morari is a Professor at the University of Padua, Italy. His research activity focusses on studying, monitoring and modelling the impact of agriculture on water, assessing the sustainability of agricultural systems, with particular reference to the physical quality of the soil, precision agriculture and soil mapping. In his presentation, Professor Morari discussed the concept of digital soil mapping, which involves

creating detailed digital representations of soil properties using advanced instruments, computational techniques, and spatial analysis methods. His discussion focused on farm-scale soil mapping, using sensors that can be towed/mounted on different platforms, allowing large portions of the field to be mapped quickly.

Giorgia Spigno, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Piacenza, Italy

Giorgia Spigno is an Associate Professor in Food Science and Technology in the Department of Food Science and Technology for a Sustainable Agri-Food Chain at the Faculty of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences of the Piacenza branch of the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore. One of her main research activities has been the valorisation of waste from the agri-food chain to produce new

ingredients and new materials for the food sector. In this workshop, Professor Spigno presented the transition from Conservation and Regenerative Agriculture to HiWeiss processing, illustrating an innovative dynamic value chain. She detailed the characterisation of various pea raw material varieties,

the protocol for isolating the HiWeiss protein, the outcomes of its extraction, and the development of some food products utilizing this protein.

Session 4 - Back to Earth

Francesco Longhi, Farmer and President of ANGA Young Farmers' Association of Veneto

Francesco Longhi is an Italian farmer and the coordinator of ANGA, the Young Farmers' Association of Veneto. During his presentation, Mr. Longhi discussed his two-year experience with implementing CA on his farm. He provided a comprehensive analysis of the strengths and weaknesses associated with this farming system.

Additionally, he proposed the innovative concept of integrating CA with precision agriculture for future advancements in the field.

Maria Rosaria Stile, Adriatica SpA, Italy

Maria Rosa Stile is a Research & Development Manager at Adriatica in Italy. In her presentation, Dr. Stile talked about the serum derived from the HiWeiss' innovative and patented plant protein extraction process, which has been proven to possess plant biostimulant activity. This

serum shows promise in enhancing plant productivity while reducing fertilizer input. The data collected by Adriatica indicate an effect of the serum in promoting plant growth, improving nutrients efficiency, and increasing plant natural tolerance to abiotic stresses.

2.2 Poster Session & 'Stretching Puzzle'

Some participants brought posters about their scientific research under the topics of the RADIANT project, which can be seen [here](#).

During the workshop, Anna showed the participants, including Italian farmers, her and HiWeiss's idea of imagining the value chain more like a puzzle than a chain, a flexible puzzle that stretches, evolves as its shape moves forward and, eventually, loops around (Figure 1). Part of the dynamism is linked to the fact that economic, environmental, and social themes are included. The final stretching puzzle can be seen [here](#). Anna is an agronomist and agricultural entrepreneur, pioneer in regenerative and CA and carbon farming & co-founder and managing partner of HiWeiss company.

Figure 1. A. Anna Trettenero, HiWeiss co-founder and **B.** Anna Trettenero, explaining stretching puzzle concept to farmers.

2.3 Round Table Discussion with Policy & Food Industry Experts

On May 17th, the day began with a round table discussion featuring policy and food industry experts. The discussion focused on various issues facing the Italian food industry, addressing challenges from economic, innovation, and sustainability perspectives. A significant topic of discussion was the shift towards a plant-based food industry, particularly in Italy, where traditional foods like pasta

hold a strong cultural significance. Participants discussed the reluctance of Italian consumers to replace or adjunct conventional wheat-based pasta with plant-based protein alternatives and emphasised the importance of preserving traditional flavours to ensure consumer acceptance. Another key discussion point was the adoption of CA and carbon farming practices among Italian farmers. The conversation explored strategies to encourage farmers to transition to these more sustainable agricultural systems. Workshop participants engaged actively in this round table discussion, as they were curious about, for example, the potential of underutilized crops in the pasta industry and methods to increase protein content in pasta.

3. Visit to HiWeiss Industrial site

On the afternoon of May 16th, participants were given a tour of the **San Nicola HiWeiss Industrial site**. HiWeiss produces plant-based proteins using two patented processes that stand out for their sustainable methodology, plus high nutritional value, and functionality - both biologically and technologically. The proteins are isolated and concentrated from non-GMO peas and soybeans and are available in gel or powder forms. The tour began with a visit of the future HiWeiss DVC processing facility, where the HiWeiss proteins produced from Yellow Pea were shown (Figure 2A). Maria Stile from Adriatica SpA then demonstrated the serum resulting from the extraction of the HiWeiss protein (Figure 2B), which can act as a biostimulant, as she had emphasised in session 4 of the workshop. Finally, the participants had the opportunity to visit the *Italmalt* barley malt production plant and understand its entire production method (Figure 2C and Figure 2D).

Figure 2. **A.** Visit at future HiWeiss DVC processing facility; **B.** Serum resulting the extraction of Pea HiWeiss protein; **C.** Italmalt facility – Adriatica SpA and **D.** Barley malt production plant.

4. Lunch prepared by Melfi Istituto Alberghiero with HiWeiss products

At the end of the workshop, students from the Melfi Istituto Alberghiero prepared a buffet lunch with HiWeiss products (protein plant-based) for all participants to enjoy (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3. Examples of dishes containing HiWeiss protein **A.** Taralli with fennel (Monococcum wheat «Verditerre»; PeaHi HiWeiss; SoyHi HiWeiss); **B.** HiWeiss Lasagna (Monococcum wheat «Verditerre»; Beta barley flour Italmalt; SoyHi HiWeiss); **C.** HiWeiss Crêpes (PeaHi HiWeiss); **D.** HiWeiss Arancini (PeaHi HiWeiss; SoyHi HiWeiss); **E.** Textured soy burger with homemade mayonnaise (PeaHi HiWeiss; SoyHi TVP HiWeiss); **F.** Chicken Rocher (SoyHi TVP HiWeiss); **G.** Tray Baked Pizza (PeaHi HiWeiss).

Figure 4. A. Menu with HiWeiss products; B. Presentation of the Menu by a student from the Melfi Istituto Alberghiero, a teacher and a chef; C. Students from the Melfi Istituto Alberghiero with Marta W. Vasconcelos (RADIANT coordinator) and Anna Trettenero (HiWeiss) and D. Workshop participants enjoying a buffet lunch with the HiWeiss menu.

5. Focus groups (Farmers and Consumers)

In the framework of **T5.3 “Farmers’ and consumers’ expectations and preferences for UCs”**, the James Hutton Institute led focus group discussions with farmers and consumers. Each discussion lasted between 1.5 and 2 hours. They started with a survey questionnaire including a **choice experiment** (DCE), followed by a **SWOT analysis** to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of upscaling the yellow pea value chain. The farmers were asked to make the same choices after the discussion, to assess the impact of increased awareness of UCs’ agroecological benefits. Below, we provide a short overview of the results of the questionnaires, and summaries of the discussions.

A. Farmers Focus Group (16th May)

Sixteen farmers took part in the activity, including two pairs managing the same farm, for a total of **14 farms**. They came primarily from the provinces of Potenza, where Melfi is located, and Foggia, located nearby. Agriculture was the main income source for all of them, and they specialized in cereals and other arable crops, possibly in addition to other crops. Their farm area ranged between 15 and 650 ha, averaging **92 ha**. Only two of them had grown yellow pea in the past, six green pea, eight chickpea, four lentil, seven fava bean, two soybean, five other legumes. In the questionnaire, they were asked to choose between hypothetical **crop rotation plans**, each prompting them to commit to a crop-rotation of cereals with one legume variety (possibly in addition to other requirements) for the next five years. Indeed, as part of the so-called “reinforced conditionality”, the 2023-2027 EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) makes crop rotations compulsory to receive the baseline payment, although farms smaller than 10 hectares are exempted. The farming plans were characterized in terms of legume to be rotated with cereals (yellow pea, green pea, chickpea), percentage of arable land to be devoted to the legume, possible presence of a sales agreement (formal or informal), possible requirement to adopt CA (that in addition to rotations, requires no till and the use of cover crops), possible inclusion of free technical

assistance, and the return per hectare. The choice data were analysed using a multinomial logistic (MNL), and the results are reported in Table 1.

We expected preference for higher returns per hectare, for free technical assistance, and for the presence of a sales agreement reducing market risk, and negative or no preference for CA, due to limited knowledge of this method. Equally we expected no significant difference between yellow and green pea, but significant positive preference for yellow pea following the collective discussion. The results show that, instead, only the percentage of land generated significant and negative impact, meaning that farmers preferred to devote a smaller area to the rotation plan; while the other attributes, including the return per hectare, did not result in a significant coefficient. However, following the discussion, in addition to the persisting **preference for a smaller area**, participants expressed significant preference for an **informal sales agreement** rather than none, and especially for **CA**, suggesting that the discussion had persuaded them of the benefits (ecological and economical) of such production practice, but not of the importance of growing yellow pea. However, none of the willingness-to-accept (WTA) values were statistically significant.

Figure 5. Left: Results of the collective SWOT analysis of the yellow pea value chain; Right: Farmers completing the choice experiment questionnaire.

The SWOT analysis identified the **presence of a supply chain** with trusted buyers, and the positive perception of legumes by the CAP, as strengths; the

possibility of limiting both market uncertainty and the impact of climate change, as opportunities. In turn, the lack of demand, the increasing frequency of droughts, the difficulty in controlling weeds when growing legumes, and **yield uncertainty** were seen as weaknesses; limited experience with the crop, the risk not to reach the minimum quality standards, and especially the **variability and lack of clarity for what concerns policy** (CAP) emerged as threats.

Table 1. Farmers' preferences for the farming plans proposed (before and after discussion).

Characteristics of the farming plan	First choice		Second choice	
	Coefficient	WTA	Coefficient	WTA
Accepting a plan (vs Not accepting)	0.166	0.177	-0.039	0.038
Variety: Yellow pea (vs Green pea)	0.517	0.553	-0.336	0.330
Variety: Chickpea (vs Green pea)	0.204	-0.218	-0.082	0.080
Share of land devoted to the plan	-1.053*	1.125	-1.914**	1.876
Sales agreement: Informal (vs None)	0.080	-0.086	0.729*	-0.715
Sales agreement: Formal (vs None)	0.455	0.486	0.607	-0.595
Conservational agriculture (vs None)	0.368	0.394	1.076***	-1.054
Technical assistance (vs None)	-0.148	0.159	0.136	-0.133
Selling price per ton (Euros)	0.936	n/a	1.020	n/a
Pseudo R-square	0.190		0.252	
Log-likelihood	-74.771		-64.084	

Notes: Baseline attribute levels in parentheses. WTA = willingness-to-accept, in 1,000 Euros. Significance levels: * 0.10, ** 0.05, *** 0.01.

Based on the farmers' responses to Likert scales, suitability for local climatic conditions would be the main driver of UC adoption, followed by the availability of technical assistance, reduced risk in returns, the presence of a premium market, and resistance to pests; in turn, other farmers' decisions were deemed unimportant. Uncertainty in input costs and selling prices was seen as the main risk, followed by adverse climatic events, pests and diseases, access to the market,

and low yields; personal issues such as health problems were not seen as a risk.¹

Differently from other UCs that represent neglected local varieties, yellow pea is an important commodity in other countries, which reduces uncertainty in terms of viability of a large-scale value chain. Nevertheless, a **critical mass** is needed to replicate this in Italy. For this reason, we asked farmers how they would behave if a local processor were to start a value chain for an UC generating agri-environmental benefits but bearing a price risk, i.e., they could get a premium only if, collectively, they would devote to it more than 50% of the available hectares. On average, the participants would have devoted 47% of their theoretically available land, but in a second farming year, they would have increased it to 62% if realising that they were slightly below the threshold. Such responses suggest that **collective action** is possible, and a critical mass can be achieved with time.

B. Consumers Focus Group (17th May)

Overall, **19 consumers** took part in the focus group discussion. Almost half came from the province of Potenza, others being from all around Italy, mostly the South. Most of them were the main person responsible for either grocery shopping or cooking in their households, and around two thirds assessed their diet as “somewhat diverse” and “somewhat healthy”, respectively. Twelve (63%) knew about yellow pea before the workshop but only four (21%) had ever consumed it, including two who had tried pasta using yellow pea flour, but with low frequency. In the DCE, they were asked to choose between hypothetical **packages of pasta** (250 grams) characterized in terms of flour type (durum wheat vs **einkorn wheat**, an ancient wheat relevant for Italy), protein type (egg vs **yellow pea gel**), nutritional value (low, middle, or high), presence of a “label of quality and territorial connection” being developed by the RADIANT partner UNISG to certify the use of UCs, environmental impact of the production process (carbon positive, neutral, or negative), place of production (locally, elsewhere in Italy, or abroad),

¹ In both Likert scales, the average ranking of the statements listed differed significantly from “neutral” at the 5% level based on a one-tailed *t*-test; the statements that did not differ significantly are not mentioned.

and price. Fifteen participants were consuming pasta several times per week, while the frequency of consuming egg pasta varied, with only one never consuming it. In line with what observed in other RADIANT workshops, we expected significant preference for lower price, higher nutritional value, local origin and, to a lesser extent, national origin. In turn, we did not make hypotheses on preferences for other characteristics, primarily the use of einkorn wheat flour and yellow pea as ingredients, since these attributes had not been tested previously. As shown in Table 2, we detected a significant preference for buying the product rather than opting out, and our hypotheses on **nutritional value** and **price** were verified but, noteworthy, we found no significant preference for local or national origin. Instead, our respondents showed aversion for carbon positive pasta, the quality label proved successful in driving choices, and the use of yellow pea gel was also a significant driver of purchase, differently from einkorn flour, which did not generate a significant coefficient. The baseline WTP was €3.22, while the premium for yellow pea was **€1.00**. Thus, despite the replacement of egg protein in making pasta could look like a “disruptive” innovation for Italian consumers, it did not face serious acceptance problems. Equally, the significance of the **environmental impact** attribute suggests that providing information on the agri-environmental benefits of UCs may increase consumers’ WTP for derived products.

Figure 6. Above: Consumers completing the choice experiment questionnaire; Right: Results of the collective SWOT analysis of the yellow pea value chain (right).

The SWOT analysis highlighted, among the strengths, the presence of structured value chain, the **healthiness** of the yellow pea protein, and the fact that it is colourless; and among the opportunities, the possibility of selling the protein product to consumers for home preparation of pasta. The weaknesses included the “status quo” bias (**habits**) of consumers, and the strong expectation of “made in Italy” being 100% Italian origin, which jointly with the current preference for short supply chains, results in the threat not to meet a rapidly growing demand, due to the **limited availability of ingredients** locally, or nationally. Noteworthy, the DCE estimates suggests that the **label** certifying territorial connection is more important than the actual origin; hence, these challenges might be overcome.

Table 2. Consumers’ preferences for types of pasta.

Characteristics of the pasta	Coefficient	WTP
Decision to purchase (vs No purchase)	1.647***	3.215***
Ingredient: Einkorn wheat (vs Durum wheat)	0.080	0.156
Protein: Yellow pea gel (vs Egg)	0.510**	0.995*
Nutritional value: Medium (vs Low)	0.705**	1.376*
Nutritional value: High (vs Low)	0.904**	1.764**
Label of quality and territorial connection (vs None)	0.506*	0.987*
Environmental impact: Carbon positive (vs Neutral)	-1.015***	-1.980**
Environmental impact: Carbon negative (vs Neutral)	0.115	0.225
Place of production: Locally (Basilicata) (vs Imported)	-0.102	-0.200
Place of production: Elsewhere in Italy (vs Imported)	0.071	0.139
Cost per package of 250 grams (Euros)	-0.512***	n/a
Pseudo R-square		0.297
Log-likelihood		-88.064

Notes: Baseline attribute levels in parentheses. WTP = willingness-to-pay, in Euros. Significance levels: * 0.10, ** 0.05, *** 0.01.

6. Annex I – Workshop Program

DAY 1 | MAY 15TH

Bus pick-up at Naples Airport at 4 pm. Additional stop at Napoli Afragola high speed train station might be set upon request.

Travel to Melfi (approximately 2 hrs) by bus

Hotel Relais La Fattoria, Melfi

Get together, aperitivo & dinner at 20:00

DAY 2 | MAY 16TH

Session 1 – Introduction 8:30 - 8:45

Welcome & Radiant-project presentation:

- Michael Atzwanger, HiWeiss president
- Marta Vasconcelos, Deputy Director of the Center for Biotechnology and Fine Chemistry (CBQF) at Universidade Católica Portuguesa (UCP)

Session 2 - Underutilised Crop Breeding and Seed Production 8:45 - 10:15

Chairperson: Pete Iannetta, The James Hutton Institute

- **Diego Rubiales**, CSIC Cordoba, Pea and faba bean breeding for Mediterranean environments
- **Paolo Annichiarico**, CREA Lodi, New pea selections for Italian environments obtained through genetical, agroecological and farmer-participatory approach
- **So_a Ghitarrini**, breeder at PSB seed company, Legume species: industrial breeding, registration of new varieties and production of certified seeds

Coffee break 10:15-10:30

Session 3 - Carbon Farming & UCs Processing 10:30 - 12:00

Chairperson: Pete Iannetta, The James Hutton Institute

- **Marco Acutis**, Università degli Studi di Milano, Monitoring soil carbon
- **Francesco Morari**, Università degli Studi di Padova, Soil mapping: state of the art and innovation
- **Giorgia Spigno**, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Piacenza, From UCs on Conservation Regenerative Agriculture to HiWeiss processing, an example of innovative dynamic value chain

Session 4 - poster & stretching puzzle 12:00 - 12:30

Chairperson: Diego Rubiales & Anna Trettenero

Lunch 12:30 - 14:30

Session 4 - Back to Earth 14:30 - 15:30

Chairperson: Anna Trettenero, HiWeiss srl/GmbH

- **Francesco Longhi**, Farmer and President of ANGA Young Farmers' Association of Veneto DVC, UCs and CA: a key for the future of farming
- **Maria Rosaria Stile**, Adriatica SpA, Looping the chain around with bio-stimulants

Session 5 - Farmers' focus group 15:30 - 17:30

JHI Farmers' focus group on yellow pea

Chairperson: Simone Piras, JHI

Session 6 - Dynamic Value Chain in Action 15:45 - 18:00

Bus leaves to San Nicola di Melfi Industrial Site

Chairperson: Giovanni Toffoli, CEO Adriatica SpA

- **Nino Catalani**, Adriatica SpA, visit to Italmalt, barley malt production plant
- **Francesco Monici**, HiWeiss srl/GmbH, HiWeiss DVC processing facility
- **Maria Rosaria Stile**, Adriatica SpA, Biostimulants & UCs crop showcase

Bus leaves back to La Fattoria

Dinner – Ristorante Lucano in Mel_ old town 20:00

Please, make sure at the desk office that you have reserved your place. Shuttle bus to the Restaurant and back to La Fattoria provided by HiWeiss

DAY 3- MAY 17TH

Session 1: Policy & Food Industry Experts 9:00 – 11:30

Chairperson: Michael Atzwanger, HiWeiss

- **Filippo Gallinella**, Former Agricultural Deputy Minister to the Italian Government
- **Gert Pomella**, WP Fine Food GmbH
- **Vito Pagnotta**, Serrocroce farming & brewing
- **Adriani SpA**, gluten-free pasta maker
- **Granoro srl**, pasta maker

Wrap up: – Marta Vasconcelos and Giovanni Toffoli.

Session 2: Consumers' focus group 10:00 - 12:00

JHI Consumers' focus group on yellow pea

Chairperson: Simone Piras, JHI

Lunch 12:00-14:00 (prepared by *Melfi Istituto Alberghiero with HiWeiss products*)

Introduction: Chef Anania and his students

The workshop is over!

Bus leaves to Naples Afragola train station and Capodichino airport at 2:30/3:00 pm depending on flight and train schedules.

